
Taiwanese Scientist Makes Mark as the "Father of Dominican Rice"

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Abstract

This article highlights the contributions of Dr. Yin T. Hsieh (謝英鐸), a Taiwanese scientist whose pioneering work in rice genetics transformed the Dominican Republic into a self-sufficient rice-producing nation. Known as the "Father of Dominican Rice," Dr. Hsieh's efforts in breeding, training, and agricultural innovation have had a lasting impact on the country's agricultural development.

Main Article

TAIPEI, Taiwan — How the Dominican Republic, a Caribbean country, became self-sufficient in rice production could be surprising, but for Dominicans there is no mystery. They know that a Taiwanese scientist contributed much for it. So, they call him the Father of Dominican Rice.

He is Dr. Yin T. Hsieh (謝英鐸), a native of Pingtung and an alumnus of National Taiwan University. Hsieh was motivated by his professor, Chao Lien-Fang, to stay two years supporting the work of the Taiwanese Technical Mission. In Taiwan, he was a rising star in rice genetics helping to develop several new varieties when the Green Revolution was booming.

Located in the Dominican Republic, the Taiwanese mission led by Hsieh and assistants in the country worked to purify the local rice cultivars that were once introduced by Spaniard conquistadores. This initial attempt helped to increase yield by 80 percent. Two years passed and the results were so promising that his professor, Chao, asked Hsieh to stay for two more years. He accepted and started a

breeding program that was to achieve unprecedented success in the region, making his research station (Juma) one of the most prolific in Latin America.

According to journalist Antonio Gil, in his book about Hsieh and the 50 years of the Taiwanese mission in the Dominican Republic, the success motivated the president of the Dominican Republic, Joaquín Balaguer, to convince Hsieh to stay longer. The impact of the Taiwanese scientists working together with Dominican colleagues is reflected in the increase of crop yield by more than 200 percent in 20 years while the whole American continent's only increased 72 percent in the same period.

This was achieved thanks to the development of a new generation of varieties combining local genetic materials with others introduced from Taiwan and other regions. The rice varieties developed by Hsieh fostered the development of a whole rice industry and more than 80 percent of the rice cultivated fields in the Dominican Republic have been growing varieties developed by Hsieh and his helpers.

They have not only created many rice varieties (best known are Juma 57, Juma 58 and Prosequisa 4), but have also educated several generations of Dominican professionals, who are now working in companies, research institutes and universities.

At the beginning, the plant breeder focused on rice yield improvement, which was barely 2.4 tons per hectare when the mission arrived in the Dominican Republic in 1965. Now, with the country self-sufficient in rice production and with a national average yield above six tons per hectare, Hsieh, at 86, works on the improvement of rice grain quality.

The title says it all. Dr. Hsieh, Father of Dominican Rice, has carefully worked to improve rice production with new rice varieties and technologies, training of local professionals and advice to the government.

Keywords

Taiwan, Dominican Republic, rice breeding, agricultural development, Yin T. Hsieh, international cooperation, food security

Citation

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By LUIS B. GOMEZ LUCIANO
Special to The China Post

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(Left) At 86, Dr. Hsieh works to improve rice grain quality in the Dominican Republic in this undated photo.

Luis B. Gomez Luciano

(Right) The author, left, is seen at the Kaohsiung research station where Hsieh worked before going to the Dominican Republic in this undated photo.

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For more information about Dr. Hsieh, visit <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1002spGILeA>